

DMP for "Artificial Intelligence Driven Face and Voice Recognition for Emotion Regulation and Stress Recovery in Athletes (ASTRA)"

Version 1

Description

This Data Management Plan (DMP) covers the data that will be collected while implementing project No. 1.1.1.9/LZP/2/25/188 "Artificial Intelligence Driven Face and Voice Recognition for Emotion Regulation and Stress Recovery in Athletes (ASTRA)" (hereinafter referred to as the Project). The aim of the Project is to develop and implement an artificial intelligence-driven system that integrates face (non-verbal) and voice (verbal) recognition technologies and psychometric assessments to monitor emotions, stress, performance, and fatigue in athletes from Latvia and Poland. Planned research outputs of the Project include experiments on raw data, experiment metadata, analysis data, and deliverable data reports. All research data collected as part of the Project is owned by the University of Latvia. The project leader will be responsible for the collection, management, and sharing of the research data.

The purpose of the DMP is to detail and ensure the preservation of the data and documents collected during the Project, as well as any results derived from it. Knowledge and data management and protection during the project will be implemented to ensure fulfillment of the requirements for security, completeness, accuracy, reliability, and consistent performance. Data will be generated locally and transferred to cloud storage (e.g., Google Drive, Microsoft cloud storage, etc.). Thus, it will be preserved and shared between postdoctoral researcher and scientific consultants from a partner organization via secure file sharing. Data will be kept for at least five years, or according to legalizations on data management, after completion of the project.

Funder

European Regional
Development Fund/ERDF

Grant

Artificial Intelligence Driven
Face and Voice Recognition for
Emotion Regulation and Stress
Recovery in Athletes (ASTRA)
(1.1.1.9/LZP/2/25/188)

Researchers

Behnam Boobani (orcid:0000-0001-8061-5088), Jurgis Skilters
(0000-0002-3235-970X), Hubert Makaruk (0000-0002-2118-4051)

Organizations

University of Latvia, Józef Piłsudski University of Physical
Education

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [DMP for "Artificial Intelligence Driven Face and Voice Recognition for Emotion Regulation and Stress Recovery in Athletes \(ASTRA\)"](#)

Description:

This Data Management Plan (DMP) covers the data that will be collected while implementing project No. 1.1.1.9/LZP/2/25/188 "Artificial Intelligence Driven Face and Voice Recognition for Emotion Regulation and Stress Recovery in Athletes (ASTRA)" (hereinafter referred to as the Project). The aim of the Project is to develop and implement an artificial intelligence-driven system that integrates face (non-verbal) and voice (verbal) recognition technologies and psychometric assessments to monitor emotions, stress, performance, and fatigue in athletes from Latvia and Poland. Planned research outputs of the Project include experiments on raw data, experiment metadata, analysis data, and deliverable data reports. All research data collected as part of the Project is owned by the University of Latvia. The project leader will be responsible for the collection, management, and sharing of the research data.

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Organizations:

University of Latvia

Józef Piłsudski University of Physical Education

Contact: Boobani Behnam (behnam.boobani@lu.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: European Regional Development Fund/ERDF

Grants: Artificial Intelligence Driven Face and Voice Recognition for Emotion Regulation and Stress Recovery in Athletes (ASTRA) (1.1.1.9/LZP/2/25/188)

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

Survey and Psychological aspects

Results from psychological and survey measures such as the recovery stress questionnaire (RESTQ), Vienna Test System (VTS), the Emotion Self-Rating Test: Geneva Wheel of Emotions, the Depression Measurement Test (PHQ9), the Fatigue Severity Scale (FSS), and a short version of the Personality Test (BFI-10) will be assessed.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

Data Management Plan | DMP for "Artificial Intelligence Driven Face and Voice Recognition for Emotion Regulation and Stress Recovery in Athletes (ASTRA)"
LICENSE:CC-BY-4.0 DOI: - 01/04/2026

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The purpose of data collection is to support the development, training, and validation of an AI-driven system by integrating facial, vocal, physiological, and psychological measures to assess athletes' emotional states, stress, and recovery processes.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Survey data
- Psychological test

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
- PDF
- CSV
- TIFF
- JPG

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

5

GB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The research outcomes align with the objectives of Latvia's Smart Specialization Strategy (RIS3, area 5), thereby improving the country's innovation capacity and the connection between academia and industry (sports clubs and federations). The research's impact is multifaceted. It can potentially influence various stakeholders within the sports industry, including athletes, coaches, sports organizations, and equipment manufacturers.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

Dublin Core

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions).

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

DataverseLV

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

Data are widely supported formats for different software tools, including open-source. SPSS.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

All formats are available for recombination with various datasets.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

2.4.3 When will the data be made available for re-use?

2029-01-31

2.4.4 How long is it intended that the data remains re-usable?

2033-01-30

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Behnam Boobani (orcid: [0000-0001-8061-5088](https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8061-5088))

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Encryption
- Firewall

- Passwords
- Physical access control

Data will be generated locally and transferred to cloud storage (e.g., Google Drive, Microsoft cloud storage, etc.), external disks, or a combination of both. Thus, it will be preserved and shared between the postdoctoral researcher and scientific consultants from a partner organization via secure file sharing and backup copying to disks. Data will be retained for at least 5 years, or in accordance with applicable data management regulations, after completion of the project.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

The research involves the collection of sensitive data, including personal information. Before participating in the study, all potential participants will receive a written participant information sheet explaining the purpose of the research, the study procedures, the type of data that will be collected, and their rights as participants. The information sheet will also clarify that participation is voluntary and that participants may withdraw from the study at any time without any negative consequences. A researcher or a trained member of the research team will explain the study and answer any questions before participation begins. The study poses minimal risk to participants. Procedures include completing questionnaires, providing brief voice samples, completing a short, computerized test, and undergoing non-invasive physiological measurements, such as heart rate variability (HRV) recordings and saliva collection for cortisol analysis. These procedures are common in psychological and sports science research and do not involve physical exertion, invasive methods, or interventions.

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.5 If yes, what are the methods used to process and access personal data/sensitive information

- Anonymising data
- Pseudonymization

Several measures will be taken to protect participants. Participation in the study will be completely voluntary, and participants may withdraw at any time without providing a reason. All procedures will be conducted in a controlled laboratory environment. Participants may skip any question they do not wish to answer. Personal data will be coded using anonymous participant identification numbers to ensure confidentiality. Facial and voice recordings will be stored securely and used only for research purposes. During the study, participants will be assigned a unique identification code, and research data will be recorded using this code. The dataset will be coded and stored in a secure, password-protected institutional repository at the University of Latvia until the end of the project or in accordance with the regulations.

Physiological/ Clinical measures

Saliva markers of cortisol levels and heart rate variability (HRV) will be measured to assess autonomic nervous system activity.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

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- Clinical data
- Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- TXT
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